

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Numerical study of convective heat transfer and of turbulent forced of different Nanofluids in channel

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Received: 25 December, 2022

Accepted: 14 January, 2022

Published: 10 January, 2022

Abstract

In this study, the flow field and heat transfer of different nanofluids (AL₂O₃, CuO, SiO₂, ZnO), turbulent forced convection in a channel. The surface of the channel is hot $T_h = 310$ K. Simulations are carried out for constant water Prandtl number of 6.99, Reynolds numbers from 20,000, 30,000, 40,000, 50,000 to 60,000, nanoparticles volume fractions of 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04 and nanoparticles diameter of 30 nm. The finite volume method and SIMPLE algorithm and k-ε are utilized to solve the governing equations numerically. The numerical results showed that with enhancing Reynolds numbers and volume fractions, average Nusselt number increases.

Keywords: Nanofluid; channel; Turbulent flow; Forced convection; Nusselt number; Numerical solution; Reynolds numbers.

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1. Introduction

Turbulent flow in the channels is the subject of importance in many engineering applications and of interest to many researchers. Some of them include energy conversion systems found in the same nuclear reactor design, heat exchangers, solar collectors, and cooling of industrial machinery and electronic components. Of great importance for the innovation of these studies in addition to experimental and numerical techniques is the research on the flow and heat transfer processes for the improvement of heat exchangers. Large-scale experimental studies of turbulent flow, heat transfer and heat exchangers have been carried out by various authors. The digital study by DIAO XU et al [1] is based on the Computational Fluid Dynamic method for improving the performance of nanofluid flows and heat transfer in micro channels. It has been found that nanoparticles improve the heat transfer of fluids by a certain percentage, and cause a sharp increase in viscous shear stress on the wall, which leads to an increase in the power to pass nanofluids into the wall. the canal. Adnan M Hussein et al [2] with the aim of improving convective turbulent heat transfer and studied

numerically the flow of the heated tube using TiO₂-water nanofluid, was used to predict the friction factor and the Nusselt number for heat transfer by forced convection of the TiO₂-water nanofluid. The Reynolds number range is 10,000 to 100,000 to be turbulent flow in a horizontal straight tube with a heat flow of 5,000 w / m². Azher M et al [3] studied numerically from a turbulent flow fully developed heat transfer behavior in trapezoidal channel systems, when using several types of nanoparticles (Al₂O₃, CuO, SiO₂, ZnO), with different volume fractions (0% to 4%), and diameter (20nm-80nm) and a heat constant of 6kw / m²; the results indicate that SiO₂ has the highest Nusselt number compared to the others. To improve heat transfer, it is a matter of increasing the volume concentration of nanoparticles and reducing the diameter if the pressure drops increase. Ajay Singh et al [4] studied numerically was carried out to observe the effect of the nanofluid on the characteristics of heat transfer by convection in the developing region of the flow of the tube, the average particle size varies from $d_p = 15$ at 150 nm and a particle concentration of 1, 2, 4, 6 and 10% were used in this work. The single-phase method with constant heat flow to the wall was